

Spin 2 Particle, Cylindric Symmetry, Projective Operator Method, External Magnetic Field

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(Received 01 July, 2023)

In the present paper we develop the theory of the massive spin 2 particle in presence of an external uniform magnetic field. We apply the matrix equation for spin 2 particle in Minkowski space-time, specifying it in cylindrical coordinates t, r, ϕ, z and tetrad formalism. By diagonalizing operators of the energy, the third projection of the total angular momentum, and the third projection of the linear momentum, we derive the system of 39 differential equations in polar coordinate r . In order to resolve this system we apply the method by Fedorov–Gronskiy based on the projective operator method. In accordance with this method, the dependance of all 39 functions is determined by only five different functions of the polar variable r , which belong to the hypergeometric type. We find in the explicit form five independent solutions of the basic matrix equation. For the energy values, we derived a 7-th order algebraic equation, it has been studied by numerical method; the physically interpretable energy values were separated.

PACS numbers: 02.30.Gp, 02.40.Ky, 03.65.Ge, 04.62.+v

Keywords: spin 2 particle, matrix formalism, external magnetic field, projective operators, exact solutions, energy spectra

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281//zenodo.10889593>

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1. Introduction

After the study by Pauli and Fierz [11], [22], the theory of massive and massless fields with spin 2 has always attracted much attention [3]–[28]. Most of the studies were performed in the framework of 2nd order differential equations. It is known that many specific difficulties may be avoided if from the very beginning we start with 1st order systems. Apparently, the first systematic study of the theory of spin 2 fields within the first order formalism was done by F. I. Fedorov [6]. It turns out that this description requires a field function with 30 independent components (remaining after taking into account the symmetries properties of the involved tensors). This theory was re-discovered by Regge [8]. The first order approach is based from the very beginning on the general theory of relativistic wave equations by the Gel'fand – Yaglom [4] and the Lagrangian formalisms.

In the present paper we develop the theory of the massive spin 2 field in presence of an external uniform magnetic field.

In Section 2 we specify the covariant matrix equation for spin 2 particle in cylindrical coordinates and tetrad; also we introduce the so called cyclic basis in the space of wave functions in which the generator J^{12} is diagonal.

In Section 3 we separate variables, by diagonalizing operators of the energy, the third projections of the linear momentum and the total angular momentum, the presence of an external uniform magnetic field is taken into account. In this way, we derive the system of the 39 the first order equations in variable r .

In Section 4 we specify the method by Fedorov–Gronskiy, to resolve this system. The method is based on the use of four projective operators allowing for decomposition of the complete wave function into the sum of 4 projective constituents. With the use of additional constraints, we transform differential equations into algebraic ones. Each constituent is determined by only one independent function. From these constrains we derive separate 2-nd

order differential equations for all four basic functions, they are solved in terms of the confluent hypergeometric functions. There arise the quantization rule for a certain intermediate parameter.

In Section 5, for energy values we derive a 7-th order algebraic equation, it is studied numerically. Depending on the amplitude of the magnetic field and quantum numbers, we find physically interpretable energy levels, besides there arise the complex energy levels which relate to anomalous solutions.

2. Spin 2 field in cylindric coordinates, the Cyclic basis

Let us consider the equation for a particle with spin 2 (see notations in [27]); in cylindric coordinates and tetrad. In the case under consideration, the basic equation reads

$$\left[\Gamma^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Gamma^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{\Gamma^2}{r} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} + J^{12} \right) + \Gamma^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial z} - M \right] \Psi = 0. \quad (1)$$

where J^{12} designates a (39×39) generator for the used set of tensors under rotation group. The cyclic basis is defined by requirement that the generator $\bar{j}^{12}$ for the vector field $\Phi = (\Phi_a)$, $a = 0, 1, 2, 3$ in this basis becomes diagonal: $\Phi_{cycl} = \bar{\Phi} = U\Phi$, $Uj^{12}U^{-1} = \bar{j}^{12}$, with

$$U = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 \end{vmatrix}, U^{-1} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where H is a scalar, H_1 is a vector Φ_a ; H_2 is a symmetric tensor Φ_{ab} , and H_3 is a 3-rank tensor $\Phi_{a[bc]}$ antisymmetric in two last indices.

The cyclic basis for tensors of 1-st, 2-nd, 3-rd ranks is determined in accordance with the

formula

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{H} \\ \bar{H}_1 \\ \bar{H}_2 \\ \bar{H}_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & U & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U \otimes U & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & U \otimes U \otimes U \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} H \\ H_1 \\ H_2 \\ H_3 \end{pmatrix};$$

therefore, the generators transform by the rules

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{J}_1^{ab} &= \bar{j}^{ab} = U j^{ab} U^{-1}, \bar{J}_2^{ab} = \bar{j}^{ab} \otimes I + I \otimes \bar{j}^{ab}, \\ \bar{J}_3^{ab} &= \bar{j}^{ab} \otimes I \otimes I + I \otimes \bar{j}^{ab} \otimes I + I \otimes I \otimes \bar{j}^{ab}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

First, we transform the needed vector generators:

$$\bar{J}_2^{12} = \begin{pmatrix} -2i & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & 0 & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & +2i & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & +i & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & 0 & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & -i & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & -i & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 0 & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & +i & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\bar{j}^{12} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\bar{J}_3^{12} = i \begin{pmatrix} -1 & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & 1 & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & 1 & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & -1 & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & -2 & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & -1 & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & -1 & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & -2 & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & -1 & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 1 & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 1 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & -1 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 1 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 2 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 2 \\ . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & . & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

3. Separation of the variables, first order system

Substitutions for separate components are

$$h(x) = e^{-ict} e^{ikz} e^{im\phi} h(r),$$

$$H_1(x) = e^{-ict} e^{ikz} e^{im\phi} \begin{pmatrix} h_0(r) \\ h_1(r) \\ h_2(r) \\ h_3(r) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$[H_2(x)](x) = e^{-iet} e^{ikz} e^{im\phi} \begin{pmatrix} f_1(r) \\ f_2(r) \\ f_3(r) \\ c_1(r) \\ c_2(r) \\ c_3(r) \\ d_1(r) \\ d_2(r) \\ d_3(r) \\ f_0(r) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{aligned} & +\sqrt{2}(d'_3 - d'_1) \Big] = Mh_0, \\ & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \frac{m}{r} c_2 + \frac{ik}{3} c_3 + \frac{i\epsilon}{3} d_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{12} \left[2 \frac{m-2}{r} f_1 + (-3h' + 2c'_2 \right. \\ & \left. - 2f'_1) \right] - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \frac{m}{r} h_0 = Mh_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$H_3(x)(x) = e^{-iet} e^{ikz} e^{im\phi} \begin{pmatrix} E_{i0}(r) \\ B_{i0}(r) \\ E_{i1}(r) \\ B_{i1}(r) \\ E_{i2}(r) \\ B_{i2}(r) \\ E_{i3}(r) \\ B_{i3}(r) \end{pmatrix}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \left[\frac{m+1}{r} c_1 + \frac{m-1}{r} c_3 \right] + \frac{1}{6} \left[3ikh + 2i\epsilon d_2 + 2ikf_2 \right. \\ & \left. + \sqrt{2}(c'_1 - c'_3) \right] = Mh_2, \\ & \frac{ik}{3} c_1 + \frac{i\epsilon}{3} d_3 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{12} \left[2 \frac{m}{r} c_2 + 2 \frac{m+2}{r} f_3 + (3h' - 2c'_2 \right. \\ & \left. + 2f'_3) \right] - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \frac{m}{r} h_0 = Mh_3; \end{aligned}$$

Correspondingly the basic equation leads to (the prime designates derivative d/dr) the following equations (1+4+10+24):

$$I, \quad -i\epsilon h_0 - ikh_2 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m+1}{r} \right) h_3$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m-1}{r} \right) h_1 = Mh;$$

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$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \left[\frac{m-1}{r} d_1 + \frac{m+1}{r} d_3 \right] + \frac{1}{6} \left[-3i\epsilon h + 2ikd_2 + 2i\epsilon f_0 \right.$$

$$\left. + B'_{21} + 2h'_1 \right] = Mf_1,$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{8} \left[3 \frac{m+1}{r} B_{12} + \frac{m-1}{r} B_{21} + \frac{1}{r} (-B_{23} + 3B_{32} - E_{10} + E_{30} + 2h_1 - 2h_3) \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{m}{r} (-B_{23} - 3B_{32} + E_{10} + E_{30} - 2h_1 - 2h_3) \right] \\ & + \frac{1}{8} [-2ikB_{11} - 2i\epsilon(E_{13} + 3E_{22} + E_{31} + 2h_0) + 2ik(B_{33} + E_{20} + 6h_2)] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +\sqrt{2}(3B'_{12} - B'_{21} - B'_{23} + 3B'_{32} - E'_{10} + E'_{30} + 2h'_1 - 2h'_3)] = Mf_2, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{m+1}{r} (B_{23} - 2h_3) - ikB_{13} - i\epsilon E_{33} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (B'_{23} - 2h'_3) = Mf_3, \\
 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \left[\frac{m+2}{r} B_{13} + \frac{m}{r} (B_{22} - B_{33} - 2h_2) \right] \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} \left[-2i\epsilon(E_{23} + E_{32}) - 2ik(B_{12} - 2h_3) + \sqrt{2}(B'_{13} - B'_{22} + B'_{33} + 2h'_2) \right] = Mc_1, \\
 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{8} \left[\frac{m+1}{r} B_{12} + \frac{m-1}{r} B_{21} + \frac{1}{r} (-B_{23} + B_{32} + E_{10} - E_{30} + 2h_1 - 2h_3) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{m}{r} (B_{23} + B_{32} + E_{10} + E_{30} + 2h_1 + 2h_3) \right] \\
 & + \frac{1}{8} [-2i\epsilon(E_{13} + E_{22} + E_{31} - 2h_0) - 2ik(B_{11} - B_{33} + E_{20} - 2h_2) \\
 & + \sqrt{2}(B'_{12} - B'_{21} - B'_{23} + B'_{32} + E'_{10} - E'_{30} + 2h'_1 - 2h'_3)] = Mc_2, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{r} B_{31} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} \frac{m}{r} (B_{11} - B_{22} - B_{31} - 2h_2) \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} \left[-2i\epsilon(E_{12} + E_{21}) + 2ik(B_{32} + 2h_1) + \sqrt{2}(B'_{11} - B'_{22} + B'_{31} - 2h'_2) \right] = Mc_3, \\
 & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \frac{m}{r} B_{20} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \left[\frac{m-2}{r} E_{11} + \frac{m}{r} (E_{31} - 2h_0) \right] \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} \left[2ik(B_{30} + E_{21}) - 2i\epsilon(E_{10} + 2h_1) - \sqrt{2}(B'_{20} + E'_{11} - E'_{31} + 2h'_0) \right] = Md_1, \\
 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \left(\frac{m+1}{r} B_{10} - \frac{m-1}{r} B_{30} + \frac{1}{r} E_{32} + \frac{m-1}{r} E_{12} + \frac{m}{r} E_{32} \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} \left[2ik(E_{22} + 2h_0) - 2i\epsilon(E_{20} + 2h_2) + \sqrt{2}(B'_{10} + B'_{30} - E'_{12} + E'_{32}) \right] = Md_2, \\
 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4} \left[\frac{m}{r} B_{20} + \frac{m}{r} E_{13} + \frac{m+2}{r} E_{33} - \frac{2m}{r} h_0 \right] \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} \left[-2ik(B_{10} - E_{23}) - 2i\epsilon(E_{30} + 2h_3) - \sqrt{2}(B'_{20} + E'_{13} - E'_{33} - 2h'_0) \right] = Md_3,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{8} \left[\frac{m+1}{r} B_{12} - \frac{m-1}{r} B_{21} + \frac{1}{r} (B_{23} + B_{32} - 3E_{10} + 3E_{30} - 2h_1 + 2h_3) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{m}{r} (B_{23} - B_{32} + 3E_{10} + 3E_{30} + 2h_1 + 2h_3) \right] \\ & + \frac{1}{8} \left[2i\epsilon(E_{13} - E_{22} + E_{31} - 6h_0) + 2ik(B_{11} - B_{33} + 3E_{20} + 2h_2) \right. \\ & \left. + \sqrt{2}(B'_{12} + B'_{21} + B'_{23} + B'_{32} - 3E'_{10} + 3E'_{30} - 2h'_1 + 2h'_3) \right] = Mf_0; \end{aligned}$$

IV

$$-i(\epsilon c_3 + kd_1) = ME_{21},$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}m}{6} \frac{c_2}{r} + \frac{ik}{3} c_3 - \frac{2i\epsilon}{3} d_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \left[3 \frac{m}{r} f_0 + \frac{m-2}{r} f_1 \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \left(2 \frac{m-1}{r} d_1 - \frac{m+1}{r} d_3 \right) - \frac{i}{6} \left[6\epsilon c_2 + 2kd_2 + 2\epsilon f_0 \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + (c'_2 + 3f'_0 - f'_1) \right] = ME_{10},$$

$$\left. \left. - i\sqrt{2}(2d'_1 + d'_3) \right] = ME_{31},$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \left(\frac{m+1}{r} c_1 + \frac{m-1}{r} c_3 \right) + \frac{1}{6} \left[-4i\epsilon d_2 - 6ikf_0 \right.$$

$$\left. - \frac{\sqrt{2}m+1}{6} \frac{c_1}{r} + \frac{2\sqrt{2}m-1}{6} \frac{c_3}{r} + \frac{i}{6} \left[6kc_2 - 2\epsilon d_2 \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + 2ikf_2 + \sqrt{2}(c'_1 - c'_3) \right] = ME_{20},$$

$$\left. \left. - 2kf_2 + i\sqrt{2}(c'_1 + 2c'_3) \right] = MB_{11},$$

$$\frac{ik}{3} c_1 - \frac{2i\epsilon}{3} d_3 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6} \left[\frac{m}{r} c_2 + 3 \frac{m}{r} f_0 + \frac{m+2}{r} f_3 \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{2\sqrt{2}m}{3} \frac{c_2}{r} + \frac{ik}{3} c_3 + \frac{i\epsilon}{3} d_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \left[(2c'_2 + f'_1) - \frac{m-2}{r} f_1 \right] \right.$$

$$\left. \left. + (-c'_2 - 3f'_0 + f'_3) \right] = ME_{30},$$

$$= MB_{21},$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{m}{r} d_2 + ikd_3 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} d'_2 = MB_{10},$$

$$- \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{m-1}{r} c_3 - ikf_1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} c'_3 = MB_{31},$$

$$- \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{m-1}{r} d_1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{m+1}{r} d_3$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{m}{r} d_2 + d'_2 \right) - i\epsilon c_3 = ME_{12},$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (d'_1 + d'_3) = MB_{20},$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}m-1}{6} \frac{d_1}{r} + \frac{\sqrt{2}m+1}{6} \frac{d_3}{r} + \frac{1}{6} \left[-4ikd_2 \right.$$

$$\left. \left. - ikd_1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{m}{r} d_2 + d'_2 \right) \right] = MB_{30},$$

$$\left. \left. + 2i\epsilon(f_0 - 3f_2) + \sqrt{2}(d'_3 - d'_1) \right] = ME_{22},$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{m-1}{r} d_1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} d'_1 - i\epsilon f_1 = ME_{11},$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{m}{r} d_2 - d'_2 \right) - i\epsilon c_1 = ME_{32},$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2ik}{3}c_1 - \frac{i\epsilon}{3}d_3 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6}\left[\frac{m}{r}c_2 - 3\frac{m}{r}f_2 + \frac{m+2}{r}f_3\right. \\ & \left. + (-c'_2 + 3f'_2 + f'_3)\right] = MB_{12}, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\left[\frac{m+1}{r}c_1 - \frac{m-1}{r}c_3 + (c'_1 + c'_3)\right] = MB_{22}, \\ & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6}\frac{m}{r}c_2 - \frac{2ik}{3}c_3 + \frac{i\epsilon}{3}d_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6}\left[\frac{m-2}{r}f_1 - 3\frac{m}{r}f_2\right. \\ & \left. + (c'_2 - f'_1 - 3f'_2)\right] = MB_{32}, \\ & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6}\left(2\frac{m+1}{r}d_3 - \frac{m-1}{r}d_1\right) + \frac{1}{6}\left[-2ikd_2\right. \\ & \left. - 2i\epsilon(3c_2 + f_0) + \sqrt{2}(d'_1 + 2d'_3)\right] = ME_{13}, \\ & -i(\epsilon c_1 + kd_3) = ME_{23}, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{m+1}{r}d_3 - i\epsilon f_3 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d'_3 = ME_{33}, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{m+1}{r}c_1 + ikf_3 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c'_1 = MB_{13}, \\ & -\frac{ik}{3}c_1 - \frac{i\epsilon}{3}d_3 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3}\left[-2\frac{m}{r}c_2 + \frac{m+2}{r}f_3\right. \\ & \left. + (2c'_2 + f'_3)\right] = MB_{23}, \\ & -\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{6}\frac{m+1}{r}c_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{6}\frac{m-1}{r}c_3 + \frac{1}{6}\left[-6ikc_2 + 2i\epsilon d_2\right. \\ & \left. + 2ikf_2 - \sqrt{2}(2c'_1 + c'_3)\right] = MB_{33}. \end{aligned}$$

4. Projective operators, the method by Fedorov–Gronskiy

Let us find the minimal equations for three generators $Y_1 = i\bar{J}_1^{12}$, $Y_2 = i\bar{J}_2^{12}$, $Y_3 = i\bar{J}_3^{12}$. We readily verify that they are of one of the same structure

$$Y_i(Y_i - 1)(Y_i + 1)(Y_i - 2)(Y_i + 2) = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$i = 1, 2, 3.$$

For each case, we introduce 5 projective operators

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 &= P_1^0 = \frac{1}{4}(Y_1 - 1)(Y_1 + 1)(Y_1 - 2)(Y_1 + 2), \\ V_2 &= P_1^{+1} = -\frac{1}{6}Y_1(Y_1 + 1)(Y_1 - 2)(Y_1 + 2), \\ V_3 &= P_1^{-1} = -\frac{1}{6}Y_1(Y_1 - 1)(Y_1 - 2)(Y_1 + 2), \\ V_4 &= P_1^{+2} = \frac{1}{24}Y_1(Y_1 - 1)(Y_1 + 1)(Y_1 + 2), \\ V_5 &= P_1^{-2} = \frac{1}{24}Y_1(Y_1 - 1)(Y_1 + 1)(Y_1 - 2); \\ S_1 &= P_2^0 = \frac{1}{4}(Y_2 - 1)(Y_2 + 1)(Y_2 - 2)(Y_2 + 2), \\ S_2 &= P_2^{+1} = -\frac{1}{6}Y_2(Y_2 + 1)(Y_2 - 2)(Y_2 + 2), \\ S_3 &= P_2^{-1} = -\frac{1}{6}Y_2(Y_2 - 1)(Y_2 - 2)(Y_2 + 2), \\ S_4 &= P_2^{+2} = \frac{1}{24}Y_2(Y_2 - 1)(Y_2 + 1)(Y_2 + 2), \\ S_5 &= P_2^{-2} = \frac{1}{24}Y_2(Y_2 - 1)(Y_2 + 1)(Y_2 - 2); \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= P_3^0 = \frac{1}{4}(Y_3 - 1)(Y_3 + 1)(Y_3 - 2)(Y_3 + 2), \\ P_2 &= P_3^{+1} = -\frac{1}{6}Y_3(Y_3 + 1)(Y_3 - 2)(Y_3 + 2), \\ P_3 &= P_3^{-1} = -\frac{1}{6}Y_3(Y_3 - 1)(Y_3 - 2)(Y_3 + 2), \\ P_4 &= P_3^{+2} = \frac{1}{24}Y_3(Y_3 - 1)(Y_3 + 1)(Y_3 + 2), \\ P_5 &= P_3^{-2} = \frac{1}{24}Y_3(Y_3 - 1)(Y_3 + 1)(Y_3 - 2). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

We need an explicit form of these projective operators, for brevity their expressions are omitted.

In accordance with the method by Fedorov–Gronskiy [10], every projective constituent should be determined by only one corresponding function of the variable r ; therefore we will apply the substitutions:

$$V_3H_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ h_3 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_3(r), \quad V_4H_1 = 0, \quad V_5H_1 = 0;$$

$$V_1H_1 = \begin{vmatrix} h_0 \\ 0 \\ h_2 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_1(r), \quad V_2H_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ h_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_2(r),$$

$$S_1H_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ f_2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ c_2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ d_2 \\ 0 \\ f_0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_1(r), \quad S_2H_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ c_3 \\ d_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_2(r), \quad S_3H_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ c_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ d_3 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_3(r), \quad S_4H_2 = \begin{vmatrix} f_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_4(r), \quad S_5H_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ f_3 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_5(r);$$

$$P_1H_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ E_{20} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{20} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{31} \\ B_{11} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{22} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{22} \\ 0 \\ E_{13} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{33} \end{vmatrix} \varphi_1(r), \quad P_2H_3 = \begin{vmatrix} E_{10} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{30} \\ 0 \\ E_{21} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{21} \\ 0 \\ E_{12} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{32} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_2(r), \quad P_3H_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{30} \\ B_{10} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{32} \\ B_{12} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{23} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{23} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_3(r), \quad P_4H_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{11} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ B_{31} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_4(r), \quad P_5H_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ E_{33} \\ B_{13} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} \varphi_5(r);$$

numerical parameters in the columns are not fixed yet, the functions $\varphi_i(r)$ will be determined below.

Now, we will act by projective operators $V_i, S_i, P_i, i = 1, \dots, 5$ on the above systems of 4, 10, and

24 equations. We will apply special notations for differential operators

$$V_1, S_1, P_1$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_m &= \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m}{r}, \quad a_{m+2} = \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m+2}{r}, \\ a_{m-1} &= \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m-1}{r}, \quad a_{m+1} = \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m+1}{r}, \\ b_m &= \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m}{r}, \quad b_{m-2} = \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m-2}{r}, \\ b_{m-1} &= \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m-1}{r}, \quad b_{m+1} = \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m+1}{r}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

We collect all equations together, at this we join them into 5 groups, referring to 5 projective operators. First we write down the first equation related to the scalar field:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1}h_1(r) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1}h_3(r) - i\epsilon h_0(r) \\ -ikh_2(r) = Mh(r) \implies \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 - i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 \\ -ikh_2\varphi_1 = Mh(r); \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - 3i\epsilon h(r) \\ + 2ikd_2\varphi_1 + 2i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 = 6Mh_0\varphi_1, \\ \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 + 3ikh(r) \\ + 2i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 + 2ikf_2\varphi_1 = 6Mh_2\varphi_1; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{12}\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{21}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{23}\varphi_3 + 3\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{32}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{10}\varphi_2 \\ + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{30}\varphi_3 + 2\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 - 2\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 - 2ikB_{11}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{13}\varphi_1 - 6i\epsilon E_{22}\varphi_1 \\ - 2i\epsilon E_{31}\varphi_1 - 4i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{33}\varphi_1 + 2ikE_{20}\varphi_1 + 12ikh_2\varphi_1 = 8Mf_2\varphi_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{12}\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{21}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{23}\varphi_3 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{32}\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{10}\varphi_2 \\ - \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{30}\varphi_3 + 2\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 - 2\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 - 2i\epsilon E_{13}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{22}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{31}\varphi_1 \\ + 4i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 - 2ikB_{11}\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{33}\varphi_1 - 2ikE_{20}\varphi_1 + 4ikh_2\varphi_1 = 8Mc_2\varphi_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{10}\varphi_3 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{30}\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{32}\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{12}\varphi_2 \\ + 2ikE_{22}\varphi_1 + 4ikh_0\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{20}\varphi_1 - 4i\epsilon h_2\varphi_1 = 4Md_2\varphi_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{12}\varphi_3 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{21}\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{23}\varphi_3 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{32}\varphi_2 - 3\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{10}\varphi_2 \\ + 3\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{30}\varphi_3 - 2\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 + 2\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 + 2i\epsilon E_{13}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{22}\varphi_1 + 2i\epsilon E_{31}\varphi_1 \\ - 12i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{11}\varphi_1 - 2ikB_{33}\varphi_1 + 6ikE_{20}\varphi_1 + 4ikh_2\varphi_1 = 8Mf_0\varphi_1; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 - \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 - ikf_0\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2\varphi_1 - ME_{20}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2\varphi_1 - ikc_2\varphi_1 + MB_{11}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}ikd_2\varphi_1 + i\epsilon c_2\varphi_1 + ME_{31}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikd_2\varphi_1 - i\epsilon c_2\varphi_1 - ME_{13}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 + i\epsilon f_2\varphi_1 + \frac{2}{3}ikd_2\varphi_1 + ME_{22}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikf_2\varphi_1 + ikc_2\varphi_1 + MB_{33}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 - MB_{22}\varphi_1 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - MB_{20}\varphi_1 = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

V_2, S_2, P_2

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sqrt{2}a_m c_2 \varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-2} f_1 \varphi_4 - \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}a_m h(r) + 2ikc_3 \varphi_2 + 2i\epsilon d_1 \varphi_2 = 6Mh_1 \varphi_2; \\
& \sqrt{2}a_m B_{11} \varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}a_m B_{22} \varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-2} B_{31} \varphi_4 - 2\sqrt{2}a_m h_2 \varphi_1 \\
& \quad - 2i\epsilon E_{12} \varphi_2 - 2i\epsilon E_{21} \varphi_2 + 2ikB_{32} \varphi_2 + 4ikh_1 \varphi_2 = 4Mc_3 \varphi_2, \\
& -\sqrt{2}a_m B_{20} \varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-2} E_{11} \varphi_4 + \sqrt{2}a_m E_{31} \varphi_1 - 2\sqrt{2}a_m h_0 \varphi_1 \\
& \quad + 2ikB_{30} \varphi_2 + 2ikE_{21} \varphi_2 - 2i\epsilon E_{10} \varphi_2 - 4i\epsilon h_1 \varphi_2 = 4Md_1 \varphi_2; \\
& \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-2} f_1 \varphi_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_m c_2 \varphi_1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m f_0 \varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 \varphi_2 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_1 \varphi_2 + ME_{10} \varphi_2 = 0, \\
& \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-2} f_1 \varphi_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_m c_2 \varphi_1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m f_2 \varphi_1 + \frac{2}{3}ikc_3 \varphi_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 \varphi_2 + MB_{32} \varphi_2 = 0, \\
& \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}a_m c_2 \varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}b_{m-2} f_1 \varphi_4 + \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 \varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 \varphi_2 - MB_{21} \varphi_2 = 0, \\
& + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m d_2 \varphi_1 - i\epsilon c_3 \varphi_2 - ME_{12} \varphi_2 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m d_2 \varphi_1 + ikd_1 \varphi_2 + MB_{30} \varphi_2 = 0, \\
& \quad i\epsilon c_3 \varphi_2 + ikd_1 \varphi_2 + ME_{21} \varphi_2 = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

V_3, S_3, P_3

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}b_m h(r) - \sqrt{2}b_m c_2 \varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+2} f_3 \varphi_5 + 2ikc_1 \varphi_3 + 2i\epsilon d_3 \varphi_3 = 6Mh_3 \varphi_3; \\
& \sqrt{2}a_{m+2} B_{13} \varphi_5 - \sqrt{2}b_m B_{22} \varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}b_m B_{33} \varphi_1 + 2\sqrt{2}b_m h_2 \varphi_1 \\
& \quad - 2i\epsilon E_{23} \varphi_3 - 2i\epsilon E_{32} \varphi_3 - 2ikB_{12} \varphi_3 + 4ikh_3 \varphi_3 = 4Mc_1 \varphi_3, \\
& -\sqrt{2}b_m B_{20} \varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}b_m E_{13} \varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+2} E_{33} \varphi_5 + 2\sqrt{2}b_m h_0 \varphi_1 \\
& \quad - 2ikB_{10} \varphi_3 + 2ikE_{23} \varphi_3 - 2i\epsilon E_{30} \varphi_3 - 4i\epsilon h_3 \varphi_3 = 4Md_3 \varphi_3;
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_m c_2 \varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+2} f_3 \varphi_5 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m f_0 \varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 \varphi_3 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_3 \varphi_3 + ME_{30} \varphi_3 = 0,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_m c_2 \varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+2} f_3 \varphi_5 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m f_2 \varphi_1 \\ + \frac{2}{3}ikc_1 \varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}ie d_3 \varphi_3 - MB_{12} \varphi_3 = 0, \\ \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}b_m c_2 \varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}a_{m+2} f_3 \varphi_5 \\ - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 \varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}ie d_3 \varphi_3 - MB_{23} \varphi_3 = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m d_2 \varphi_1 - ikd_3 \varphi_3 + MB_{10} \varphi_3 = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m d_2 \varphi_1 + i\epsilon c_1 \varphi_3 + ME_{32} \varphi_3 = 0, \\ i\epsilon c_1 \varphi_3 + ikd_3 \varphi_3 + ME_{23} \varphi_3 = 0; \end{aligned}$$

V_4, S_4, P_4

$$\begin{aligned} a_{m-1}B_{21} \varphi_2 + 2a_{m-1}h_1 \varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{31} \varphi_4 \\ + \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{11} \varphi_4 = -\sqrt{2}Mf_1 \varphi_4, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1}d_1 \varphi_2 - i\epsilon f_1 \varphi_4 - ME_{11} \varphi_4 = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1}c_3 \varphi_2 + ikf_1 \varphi_4 + MB_{31} \varphi_4 = 0; \end{aligned}$$

V_5, S_5, P_5

$$\begin{aligned} -b_{m+1}B_{23} \varphi_3 + 2b_{m+1}h_3 \varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{13} \varphi_5 \\ - \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{33} \varphi_5 = \sqrt{2}Mf_3 \varphi_5, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1}d_3 \varphi_3 + i\epsilon f_3 \varphi_5 + ME_{33} \varphi_5 = 0, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1}c_1 \varphi_3 - ikf_3 \varphi_5 + MB_{13} \varphi_5 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

In accordance with the method by Fedorov

– Gronskiy [10], this system should be consistent with the following differential constraints (they permit us to transform all differential equations into algebraic ones after dividing by total multipliers):

$$\begin{aligned} b_{m-1} \varphi_2(r) = C_1 \varphi_1(r), \quad a_{m+1} \varphi_3(r) = C_2 \varphi_1(r); \\ a_m \varphi_1(r) = C_3 \varphi_2(r), \quad b_{m-2} \varphi_4(r) = C_4 \varphi_2(r); \\ b_m \varphi_1(r) = C_5 \varphi_3(r), \quad a_{m+2} \varphi_5(r) = C_6 \varphi_3(r); \\ a_{m-1} \varphi_2 = C_7 \varphi_4, \quad b_{m+1} \varphi_3 = C_8 \varphi_5; \\ h(r) = h \varphi_1(r). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In this way we derive (restrictions $h_1 \equiv 0, h_3 \equiv 0$ will be taken into account later):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}h_1 C_7 \varphi_4 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}h_3 C_8 \varphi_5 - i\epsilon h_0 \varphi_1 - ikh_2 \varphi_1 \\ = Mh \varphi_1; \end{aligned}$$

V_1, S_1, P_1

$$\begin{aligned} -\sqrt{2}d_1 C_1 + \sqrt{2}d_3 C_2 - 3i\epsilon h + 2ikd_2 + 2i\epsilon f_0 \\ = 6Mh_0, \\ \sqrt{2}c_1 C_2 - \sqrt{2}c_3 C_1 + 3ikh + 2i\epsilon d_2 + 2ikf_2 \\ = 6Mh_2; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3\sqrt{2}B_{12}C_2 - \sqrt{2}B_{21}C_1 - \sqrt{2}B_{23}C_2 + 3\sqrt{2}B_{32}C_1 - \sqrt{2}E_{10}C_1 + \sqrt{2}E_{30}C_2 + 2\sqrt{2}h_1C_1 - 2\sqrt{2}h_3C_2 \\ - 2ikB_{11} - 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 6i\epsilon E_{22} - 2i\epsilon E_{31} - 4i\epsilon h_0 + 2ikB_{33} + 2ikE_{20} + 12ikh_2 = 8Mf_2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}B_{12}C_2 - \sqrt{2}B_{21}C_1 - \sqrt{2}B_{23}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{32}C_1 + \sqrt{2}E_{10}C_1 - \sqrt{2}E_{30}C_2 + 2\sqrt{2}h_1C_1 - 2\sqrt{2}h_3C_2 \\ - 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 2i\epsilon E_{22} - 2i\epsilon E_{31} + 4i\epsilon h_0 - 2ikB_{11} + 2ikB_{33} - 2ikE_{20} + 4ikh_2 = 8Mc_2, \end{aligned}$$

$$\sqrt{2}B_{10}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{30}C_1 + \sqrt{2}E_{32}C_2 - \sqrt{2}E_{12}C_1 + 2ikE_{22} + 4ikh_0 - 2i\epsilon E_{20} - 4i\epsilon h_2 = 4Md_2,$$

$$\sqrt{2}B_{12}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{21}C_1 + \sqrt{2}B_{23}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{32}C_1 - 3\sqrt{2}E_{10}C_1 + 3\sqrt{2}E_{30}C_2 - 2\sqrt{2}h_1C_1 + 2\sqrt{2}h_3C_2 + 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 2i\epsilon E_{22} + 2i\epsilon E_{31} - 12i\epsilon h_0 + 2ikB_{11} - 2ikB_{33} + 6ikE_{20} + 4ikh_2 = 8Mf_0;$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_1C_2 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_3C_1 - \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_2 - ikf_0 \\ + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 - ME_{20} = 0, \\ \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_1C_2 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}c_3C_1 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 \\ - ikc_2 + MB_{11} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}d_1C_1 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_3C_2 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 + \frac{1}{3}ikd_2 \\ + i\epsilon c_2 + ME_{31} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_1C_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}d_3C_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 - \frac{1}{3}ikd_2 \\ - i\epsilon c_2 - ME_{13} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_1C_1 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_3C_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 + i\epsilon f_2$$

$$+ \frac{2}{3}ikd_2 + ME_{22} = 0,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}c_1C_2 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_3C_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2 - \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 \\ + ikc_2 + MB_{33} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_1C_2 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_3C_1 - MB_{22} = 0,$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_1C_1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_3C_2 - MB_{20} = 0;$$

V_2, S_2, P_2

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}c_2C_3 - \sqrt{2}f_1C_4 - \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}hC_3 + 2ikc_3 + 2i\epsilon d_1 \\ = 6Mh_1; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}B_{11}C_3 - \sqrt{2}B_{22}C_3 + \sqrt{2}B_{31}C_4 - 2\sqrt{2}h_2C_3 \\ - 2i\epsilon E_{12} - 2i\epsilon E_{21} + 2ikB_{32} + 4ikh_1 = 4Mc_3, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\sqrt{2}B_{20}C_3 - \sqrt{2}E_{11}C_4 + \sqrt{2}E_{31}C_3 - 2\sqrt{2}h_0C_3 \\ + 2ikB_{30} + 2ikE_{21} - 2i\epsilon E_{10} - 4i\epsilon h_1 = 4Md_1; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_1C_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_3 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_0C_3 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 \\ + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_1 + ME_{10} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_1C_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_2C_3 + \frac{2}{3}ikc_3 \\ - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 + MB_{32} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}c_2C_3 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}f_1C_4 + \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 \\ + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 - MB_{21} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_3 - i\epsilon c_3 - ME_{12} = 0,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_3 + ikd_1 + MB_{30} = 0, \\ i\epsilon c_3 + ikd_1 + ME_{21} = 0; \end{aligned}$$

V_3, S_3, P_3

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}hC_5 - \sqrt{2}c_2C_5 + \sqrt{2}f_3C_6 + 2ikc_1 \\ + 2i\epsilon d_3 = 6Mh_3, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2}B_{13}C_6 - \sqrt{2}B_{22}C_5 + \sqrt{2}B_{33}C_5 + 2\sqrt{2}h_2C_5 \\ - 2i\epsilon E_{23} - 2i\epsilon E_{32} - 2ikB_{12} + 4ikh_3 = 4Mc_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\sqrt{2}B_{20}C_5 - \sqrt{2}E_{13}C_5 + \sqrt{2}E_{33}C_6 + 2\sqrt{2}h_0C_5 \\ - 2ikB_{10} + 2ikE_{23} - 2i\epsilon E_{30} - 4i\epsilon h_3 = 4Md_3; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_5 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_3C_6 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_0C_5 \\
 & - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_3 + ME_{30} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_5 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_3C_6 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_2C_5 \\
 & + \frac{2}{3}ikc_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 - MB_{12} = 0, \\
 & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}c_2C_5 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}f_3C_6 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 \\
 & - MB_{23} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_5 - ikd_3 + MB_{10} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_5 + i\epsilon c_1 + ME_{32} = 0, \\
 & i\epsilon c_1 + ikd_3 + ME_{23} = 0;
 \end{aligned}$$

V_4, S_4, P_4

$$\begin{aligned}
 & B_{21}C_7 + 2h_1C_7 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{31} + \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{11} \\
 & = -\sqrt{2}Mf_1; \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_1C_7 - i\epsilon f_1 - ME_{11} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_3C_7 + ikf_1 + MB_{31} = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

V_5, S_5, P_5

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -B_{23}C_8 + 2h_3C_8 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{13} - \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{33} \\
 & = \sqrt{2}Mf_3; \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_3C_8 + i\epsilon f_3 + ME_{33} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_1C_8 - ikf_3 + MB_{13} = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now let us turn to differential constraints, grouping them differently:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & b_{m-1}\varphi_2 = C_1\varphi_1, \quad a_m\varphi_1 = C_3\varphi_2; \\
 & a_{m+1}\varphi_3 = C_2\varphi_1, \quad b_m\varphi_1 = C_5\varphi_3; \\
 & b_{m-2}\varphi_4 = C_4\varphi_2, \quad a_{m-1}\varphi_2 = C_7\varphi_4; \\
 & a_{m+2}\varphi_5 = C_6\varphi_3, \quad b_{m+1}\varphi_3 = C_8\varphi_5;
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

these relations permit us to derive second order

equations for separate functions

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (b_{m-1}a_m - C_1C_3)\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & (a_mb_{m-1} - C_1C_3)\varphi_2 = 0; \\
 & (a_{m+1}b_m - C_2C_5)\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & (b_ma_{m+1} - C_2C_5)\varphi_3 = 0; \\
 & (b_{m-2}a_{m-1} - C_4C_7)\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & (a_{m-1}b_{m-2} - C_4C_7)\varphi_4 = 0; \\
 & (a_{m+2}b_{m+1} - C_6C_8)\varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & (b_{m+1}a_{m+2} - C_6C_8)\varphi_5 = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Because within each pair C_1, C_3 ; C_2, C_5 ; C_4, C_7 ; C_6, C_8 the parameters are defined up to inverse multipliers, for each pair these parameters may be chosen as equal to each other:

$$C_1 = C_3, \quad C_2 = C_5, \quad C_4 = C_7, \quad C_6 = C_8. \tag{11}$$

Therefore the above equations take the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (b_{m-1}a_m - C_3^2)\varphi_1 = 0, \quad (a_{m+1}b_m - C_5^2)\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & (a_mb_{m-1} - C_3^2)\varphi_2 = 0, \quad (b_{m-2}a_{m-1} - C_7^2)\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & (b_ma_{m+1} - C_5^2)\varphi_3 = 0, \quad (a_{m+2}b_{m+1} - C_8^2)\varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & (a_{m-1}b_{m-2} - C_7^2)\varphi_4 = 0, \quad (b_{m+1}a_{m+2} - C_8^2)\varphi_5 = 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

For each function from $\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3$ we have two equations, which assume that there should exist relationships between the corresponding parameters.

In this point, let us take into account the presence of an external magnetic field in eq. (1). Since in cylindrical coordinates for magnetic field we have expression $A_\phi = \frac{Br^2}{2}$, we should make one formal change, $m \implies m + eBr^2/2$ (for shortness we change the notation $eB \implies B$).

Further, we specify the products of the operators:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_1 &= b_{m-1}a_m = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2r^2}{4} - Bm \\
 & \quad + B - \frac{m^2}{r^2}, \\
 Q'_1 &= a_{m+1}b_m = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2r^2}{4} - Bm \\
 & \quad - B - \frac{m^2}{r^2}, \\
 Q_1 - Q'_1 &= 2B, \implies Q'_1 = Q_1 - 2B;
 \end{aligned}$$

$$Q_2 = a_m b_{m-1} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{4} - Bm - \frac{m^2}{r^2} + \frac{2m}{r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2},$$

$$Q'_2 = b_{m-2} a_{m-1} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{4} - Bm - \frac{m^2}{r^2} + \frac{2m}{r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} + 2B,$$

$$Q_2 - Q'_2 = -2B \implies Q'_2 = Q_2 + 2B;$$

$$Q_3 = b_m a_{m+1} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{4} - Bm - \frac{m^2}{r^2} - \frac{2m}{r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2},$$

$$Q'_3 = a_{m+2} b_{m+1} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{4} - Bm - \frac{m^2}{r^2} - \frac{2m}{r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} - 2B,$$

$$Q_3 - Q'_3 = 2B \implies Q'_3 = Q_3 - 2B;$$

$$Q_4 = a_{m-1} b_{m-2} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{4} - Bm + B - \frac{m^2}{r^2} + \frac{4m}{r^2} - \frac{4}{r^2};$$

$$Q_5 = b_{m+1} a_{m+2} = \frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{4} - Bm - B - \frac{m^2}{r^2} - \frac{4m}{r^2} - \frac{4}{r^2}.$$

Correspondingly, the second-order equations are presented as follows

$$(Q_1 - C_3^2)\varphi_1 = 0, (Q_1 - 2B - C_5^2)\varphi_1 = 0 \implies C_5^2 = C_3^2 - 2B;$$

$$(Q_2 - C_3^2)\varphi_2 = 0, (Q_2 + 2B - C_7^2)\varphi_2 = 0 \implies C_7^2 = C_3^2 + 2B; \quad (13)$$

$$(Q_3 - C_5^2)\varphi_3 = 0, (Q_3 - 2B - C_8^2)\varphi_3 = 0 \implies C_8^2 = C_5^2 - 2B = C_3^2 - 4B;$$

$$(Q_4 - C_7^2)\varphi_4 = 0, (Q_5 - C_8^2)\varphi_5 = 0.$$

Among four parameters $C_3^2, C_5^2, C_7^2, C_8^2$ one can choose the parameter C_3^2 as a main one

$$C_3^2 = X, C_5^2 = X - 2B, C_7^2 = X + 2B, \quad (14)$$

$$C_8^2 = X - 4B. \quad (15)$$

Thus, we have five different equations:

$$\begin{aligned} (Q_1 - X)\varphi_1 &= 0, (Q_2 - X)\varphi_2 = 0, \\ (Q_3 - X + 2B)\varphi_3 &= 0, \\ (Q_4 - X - 2B)\varphi_4 &= 0, (Q_5 - X + 4B)\varphi_5 = 0, \\ X &= C_3^2. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

In the new variable $z = Br^2/2$ they take the form

$$\begin{aligned} &\left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{(m/2)^2}{z^2} - \frac{m/2}{z} + \frac{1}{2z} \left(1 - \frac{X}{B}\right) \right] \varphi_1 = 0, \\ &\left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{[(m-1)/2]^2}{z^2} - \frac{(m+1)/2}{z} + \frac{1}{2z} \left(1 - \frac{X}{B}\right) \right] \varphi_2 = 0, \\ &\left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{[(m+1)/2]^2}{z^2} - \frac{(m-1)/2}{z} + \frac{1}{2z} \left(1 - \frac{X}{B}\right) \right] \varphi_3 = 0, \\ &\left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{[(m-2)/2]^2}{z^2} - \frac{(m+2)/2}{z} + \frac{1}{2z} \left(1 - \frac{X}{B}\right) \right] \varphi_4 = 0, \\ &\left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{[(m+2)/2]^2}{z^2} - \frac{(m-2)/2}{z} + \frac{1}{2z} \left(1 - \frac{X}{B}\right) \right] \varphi_5 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Instead of the choice (15)

$$C_3^2 = X, C_5^2 = X - 2B, C_7^2 = X + 2B, \quad (18)$$

$$C_8^2 = X - 4B, \quad (19)$$

one may introduce other primary parameter Y , $X = Y + B$, then we have more symmetric constraints

$$C_3^2 = Y + B, \quad (20)$$

$$C_5^2 = Y - B, \quad (21)$$

$$C_7^2 = Y + 3B, \quad (22)$$

$$C_8^2 = Y - 3B. \quad (23)$$

All equations in (17) have the same general structure. Behavior of the solutions near the

points $z = 0$ and $z = \infty$ are described by the following relations:

$$\varphi_1 = z^{+|m|/2}, \varphi_2 = z^{+|m-1|/2}, \varphi_3 = z^{+|m+1|/2}, \\ \varphi_4 = z^{+|m-2|/2}, \varphi_5 = z^{+|m+2|/2}$$

and

$$\varphi_i(z \rightarrow \infty) = e^{-z/2}, i = 1, \dots, 5,$$

respectively. Solutions of the all five equations are searched in the form $\varphi = z^A e^{-z/2} F$, further we obtain

$$\left[z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} + (2A_1 + 1 - z) \frac{d}{dz} - A_1 - \frac{m}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{X}{B} \right] F_1 = 0, \\ \left[z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} + (2A_2 + 1 - z) \frac{d}{dz} - A_2 - (m+1)/2 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{X}{B} \right] F_2 = 0, \\ \left[z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} + (2A_3 + 1 - z) \frac{d}{dz} - A_3 - (m-1)/2 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{X}{B} \right] F_3 = 0, \\ \left[z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} + (2A_4 + 1 - z) \frac{d}{dz} - A_4 - (m+2)/2 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{X}{B} \right] F_4 = 0, \\ \left[z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} + (2A_5 + 1 - z) \frac{d}{dz} - A_5 - (m-2)/2 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{X}{B} \right] F_5 = 0,$$

$$A_1 = +|m|/2, A_2 = +|m-1|/2, A_3 = +|m+1|/2, \\ A_4 = +|m-2|/2, A_5 = +|m+2|/2.$$

Taking in mind the standard form of the confluent hypergeometric equation

$$zF_i'' + (\gamma_i - z)F_i' - \alpha_i F_i = 0, i = 1, \dots, 5;$$

for the parameters α_i, γ_i we have the following

expressions

$$\gamma_1 = 2A_1 + 1 = |m| + 1, \alpha_1 = \frac{1}{2}(|m| + m + \frac{X}{B}); \\ \gamma_2 = 2A_2 + 1 = |m-1| + 1, \\ \alpha_2 = \frac{1}{2}(|m-1| + m + 1 + \frac{X}{B}); \\ \gamma_3 = 2A_3 + 1 = |m+1| + 1, \\ \alpha_3 = \frac{1}{2}(|m+1| + m - 1 + \frac{X}{B}); \\ \gamma_4 = 2A_4 + 1 = |m-2| + 1, \\ \alpha_4 = \frac{1}{2}(|m-2| + m + 2 + \frac{X}{B}); \\ \gamma_5 = 2A_5 + 1 = |m+2| + 1, \\ \alpha_5 = \frac{1}{2}(|m+2| + m - 2 + \frac{X}{B}).$$

Applying the polynomial condition $\alpha_i = -n_i, n_i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, we get five quantization rules

$$X = -2B(n_1 + \frac{|m| + m}{2}) = -2BN_1 < 0, \\ n_1 = 1, 2, 3, \dots; \\ X = -2B(n_2 + \frac{|m-1| + m + 1}{2}) = -2BN_2 < 0, \\ n_2 = 1, 2, 3, \dots; \\ X = -2B(n_3 + \frac{|m+1| + m - 1}{2}) = -2BN_3 < 0, \\ n_3 = 1, 2, 3, \dots; \\ X = -2B(n_4 + \frac{|m-2| + m + 2}{2}) = -2BN_4 < 0, \\ n_4 = 1, 2, 3, \dots; \\ X = -2B(n_5 + \frac{|m+2| + m - 2}{2}) = -2BN_5 < 0, \\ n_5 = 1, 2, 3, \dots. \quad (24)$$

In all formulas (24), the quantity X is the same, though written in different forms. Below we will consider the most simple expression for X as basic one:

$$X = -2B(n_1 + \frac{|m| + m}{2}) = -2BN_1 < 0, \quad (25) \\ n_1 \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}.$$

5. Studying the complete algebraic system

Let us turn to the above algebraic system. It is convenient to apply dimensionless quantities:

$$\frac{M}{M} \Rightarrow 1, \quad \frac{C_i}{M} \Rightarrow C_i, \quad \frac{X}{M^2} \Rightarrow X, \quad \frac{B}{M^2} \Rightarrow B, \\ \frac{\epsilon}{M} \Rightarrow \epsilon, \quad \frac{k}{M} \Rightarrow k. \quad (26)$$

Correspondingly, the algebraic system reads

$$h_1 = 0, \quad h_3 = 0, \quad -i\epsilon h_0 - ikh_2 = h;$$

$$V_1, S_1, P_1$$

$$-\sqrt{2}d_1C_1 + \sqrt{2}d_3C_2 - 3i\epsilon h + 2ikd_2 + 2i\epsilon f_0 = 6h_0,$$

$$\sqrt{2}c_1C_2 - \sqrt{2}c_3C_1 + 3ikh + 2i\epsilon d_2 + 2ikf_2 = 6h_2;$$

$$\begin{aligned} & 3\sqrt{2}B_{12}C_2 - \sqrt{2}B_{21}C_1 - \sqrt{2}B_{23}C_2 + 3\sqrt{2}B_{32}C_1 - \sqrt{2}E_{10}C_1 \\ & + \sqrt{2}E_{30}C_2 + 2\sqrt{2}h_1C_1 - 2\sqrt{2}h_3C_2 - 2ikB_{11} - 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 6i\epsilon E_{22} \\ & - 2i\epsilon E_{31} - 4i\epsilon h_0 + 2ikB_{33} + 2ikE_{20} + 12ikh_2 = 8f_2, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{12}C_2 - \sqrt{2}B_{21}C_1 - \sqrt{2}B_{23}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{32}C_1 + \sqrt{2}E_{10}C_1 \\ & - \sqrt{2}E_{30}C_2 + 2\sqrt{2}h_1C_1 - 2\sqrt{2}h_3C_2 - 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 2i\epsilon E_{22} - 2i\epsilon E_{31} \\ & + 4i\epsilon h_0 - 2ikB_{11} + 2ikB_{33} - 2ikE_{20} + 4ikh_2 = 8c_2, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{10}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{30}C_1 + \sqrt{2}E_{32}C_2 - \sqrt{2}E_{12}C_1 \\ & + 2ikE_{22} + 4ikh_0 - 2i\epsilon E_{20} - 4i\epsilon h_2 = 4d_2, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{12}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{21}C_1 + \sqrt{2}B_{23}C_2 + \sqrt{2}B_{32}C_1 - 3\sqrt{2}E_{10}C_1 \\ & + 3\sqrt{2}E_{30}C_2 - 2\sqrt{2}h_1C_1 + 2\sqrt{2}h_3C_2 + 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 2i\epsilon E_{22} + 2i\epsilon E_{31} - 12i\epsilon h_0 + 2ikB_{11} - 2ikB_{33} + 6ikE_{20} + 4ikh_2 = 8f_0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_1C_2 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_3C_1 - \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_2 - ikf_0 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 - E_{20} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_1C_2 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}c_3C_1 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 - ikc_2 + B_{11} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}d_1C_1 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_3C_2 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 + \frac{1}{3}ikd_2 + i\epsilon c_2 + E_{31} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_1C_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}d_3C_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 - \frac{1}{3}ikd_2 - i\epsilon c_2 - E_{13} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_1C_1 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_3C_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 + i\epsilon f_2 + \frac{2}{3}ikd_2 + E_{22} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}c_1C_2 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_3C_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2 - \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 + ikc_2 + B_{33} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_1C_2 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_3C_1 - B_{22} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_1C_1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_3C_2 - B_{20} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

V_2, S_2, P_2

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{2}c_2C_3 - \sqrt{2}f_1C_4 - \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}hC_3 + 2ikc_3 + 2iEd_1 = 6h_1, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{11}C_3 - \sqrt{2}B_{22}C_3 + \sqrt{2}B_{31}C_4 - 2\sqrt{2}h_2C_3 - 2i\epsilon E_{12} - 2i\epsilon E_{21} + 2ikB_{32} + 4ikh_1 = 4c_3, \\ & -\sqrt{2}B_{20}C_3 - \sqrt{2}E_{11}C_4 + \sqrt{2}E_{31}C_3 - 2\sqrt{2}h_0C_3 + 2ikB_{30} + 2ikE_{21} - 2i\epsilon E_{10} - 4ich_1 = 4d_1, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_1C_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_3 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_0C_3 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_1 + E_{10} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_1C_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_2C_3 + \frac{2}{3}ikc_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 + B_{32} = 0, \\ & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}c_2C_3 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}f_1C_4 + \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 - B_{21} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_3 - i\epsilon c_3 - E_{12} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_3 + ikd_1 + B_{30} = 0, \quad i\epsilon c_3 + ikd_1 + E_{21} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

V_3, S_3, P_3

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}hC_5 - \sqrt{2}c_2C_5 + \sqrt{2}f_3C_6 + 2ikc_1 + 2i\epsilon d_3 = 6h_3; \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{13}C_6 - \sqrt{2}B_{22}C_5 + \sqrt{2}B_{33}C_5 + 2\sqrt{2}h_2C_5 - 2i\epsilon E_{23} - 2i\epsilon E_{32} - 2ikB_{12} + 4ikh_3 = 4c_1, \\ & -\sqrt{2}B_{20}C_5 - \sqrt{2}E_{13}C_5 + \sqrt{2}E_{33}C_6 + 2\sqrt{2}h_0C_5 - 2ikB_{10} + 2ikE_{23} - 2i\epsilon E_{30} - 4ich_3 = 4d_3, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_5 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_3C_6 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_0C_5 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_3 + E_{30} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2C_5 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_3C_6 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_2C_5 + \frac{2}{3}ikc_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 - B_{12} = 0, \\ & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}c_2C_5 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}f_3C_6 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 - B_{23} = 0, \quad + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_5 - ikd_3 + B_{10} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2C_5 + i\epsilon c_1 + E_{32} = 0, \quad i\epsilon c_1 + ikd_3 + E_{23} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

V_4, S_4, P_4

$$\begin{aligned} & B_{21}C_7 + 2h_1C_7 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{31} + \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{11} = -\sqrt{2}f_1, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_1C_7 - i\epsilon f_1 - E_{11} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_3C_7 + ikf_1 + B_{31} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

V_5, S_5, P_5

$$-B_{23}C_8 + 2h_3C_8 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{13} - \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{33} = \sqrt{2}f_3,$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_3C_8 + i\epsilon f_3 + E_{33} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_1C_8 - ikf_3 + B_{13} = 0.$$

Let us take into account that from irreducibility of the second rank tensor, $\Phi_a^a = 0$ (for more detail see in [27]), it follows the constraint (here we apply constraint recalculated to cyclic basis)

$$f_0 - f_2 + 2c_2 \equiv 0; \quad (27)$$

we readily verify that the combination of

corresponding equations in accordance with (27), we obtain the identity $0 \equiv 0$. Therefore, from the algebraic system we can eliminate one equation, let it be the first equation from the last three. In remaining equations, instead of f_0 we set $f_0 = f_2 - 2c_2$. Besides, in the algebraic system we should take into account the relations between parameters (recall that $X = -2BN$):

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 = C_3 = \sqrt{X}, \quad C_2 = C_5 = \sqrt{X - 2B}, \\ C_4 = C_7 = \sqrt{X + 2B}, \quad C_6 = C_8 = \sqrt{X - 4B}; \\ C_1 = C_3 = \sqrt{Y + B}, \quad C_2 = C_5 = \sqrt{Y - B}, \\ C_4 = C_7 = \sqrt{Y + 3B}, \quad C_6 = C_8 = \sqrt{Y - 3B}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

To simplify the problem, we apply the following

method. From the first equation of the complete system we express the variable h through h_0 and h_2 , besides we set $h_1 = 0, h_3 = 0$. Then we eliminate the following variables

$$\begin{aligned} h_0, h_2, E_{20}, B_{11}, E_{31}, E_{13}, E_{22}, B_{33}, B_{22}, B_{20}; \\ E_{10}, B_{32}, B_{21}, E_{12}, B_{30}, E_{21}; \\ E_{30}, B_{12}, B_{23}, B_{10}, E_{32}, E_{23}; \end{aligned}$$

$$E_{11}, B_{31}; E_{33}, B_{13}.$$

After performing the needed calculations, we derive the linear algebraic system of 12 equations for 10 variables:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}(2k^2-4\epsilon^2-7)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_1 + (4k^2 - \frac{4}{3}(3\epsilon^2+Y))c_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}(2k^2-4\epsilon^2-7)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_3 \\ + \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-4k^2+2\epsilon^2+5)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_1 + \frac{16k\epsilon(2\epsilon^2+3)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-4k^2+2\epsilon^2+5)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_3 \\ + \frac{[-2\epsilon^4+6(2k^2+Y-2)\epsilon^2+6(k^2-2)(k^2-Y)]}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_0 - \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 \\ + \frac{2}{3}\left[-11k^2-9\epsilon^2-9Y + \frac{4k^2-8k^4}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2} - 12\right]f_2 - \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B}f_3 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}c_1 + (4k^2 - \frac{4}{3}(3\epsilon^2+Y+6))c_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}c_3 \\ - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}d_1 + \frac{16}{3}k\epsilon\left(\frac{1}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2} - 1\right)d_2 + \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}d_3 \\ + \frac{2}{3}\left(-3k^2-\epsilon^2+3Y + \frac{8-4k^2}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2} - 4\right)f_0 - \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 \\ + \left[\frac{2}{3}k^2\left(\frac{4}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2} - 1\right) - 2(\epsilon^2+Y)\right]f_2 - \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B}f_3 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}c_1 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}c_3 \\ - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_1 - \frac{4[k^2(4\epsilon^2+3Y+3) - 3(Y+1)(\epsilon^2+2)]}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 \\ + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_3 + \frac{4k\epsilon(-3k^2+\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_0 + \left(\frac{8\epsilon k^3}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6} + 4\epsilon k\right)f_2 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}(2k^2-4\epsilon^2-5)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_1 + \left(-4k^2+4\epsilon^2+\frac{4Y}{3}\right)c_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}(2k^2-4\epsilon^2-5)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_3 \\
 & + \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-4k^2+2\epsilon^2+7)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_1 + \frac{16k(2k^2-3)\epsilon}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-4k^2+2\epsilon^2+7)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_3 \\
 & + \frac{2}{3}\left[k^2+3\epsilon^2-9Y+\frac{4(2k^4-7k^2+6)}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}\right]f_0 + \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 \\
 & + \left[-\frac{2(k^2-9\epsilon^2-6)k^2}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}-2(\epsilon^2+Y)\right]f_2 + \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B}f_3 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{i\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}k}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}c_1 + \sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}c_2 + i\left(\frac{B+Y}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}+2\right)kc_3 \\
 & + i\epsilon\left(\frac{B+Y}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}+2\right)d_1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}d_2 + \frac{i\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}d_3 \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}f_0 - \sqrt{2}\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}k^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}f_2 = 0, \\
 & + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-2k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_1 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}c_2 \\
 & + \frac{2}{3}\left[\frac{(B+Y)k^2}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}+2k^2-6B-3(2\epsilon^2+Y+2)\right]c_3 + \frac{2}{3}k\left(\frac{B+Y}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}-4\right)\epsilon d_1 \\
 & - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)\epsilon}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_2 + \frac{2k\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_3 \\
 & + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon^2}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_0 - \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}[2k^2-3(\epsilon^2+2)]}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_2 = 0, \\
 & \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}c_1 - \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon c_2 + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon\left(\frac{B+Y}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}+4\right)kc_3 \\
 & + \frac{2}{3}\left[6k^2-2\epsilon^2-7B-4Y+\frac{(k^2-2)(B+Y)}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}-6\right]d_1 \\
 & - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)k}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-3k^2+2\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_3 \\
 & - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-3k^2+2\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}f_0 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{3B+Y}\epsilon f_1 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k^2}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}f_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & i\left(\frac{B-Y}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}+2\right)kc_1 - \sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}c_2 + \frac{i\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}k}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}c_3 \\
 & + \frac{i\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}d_1 + \frac{2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon k}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}d_2 + i\epsilon\left(\frac{B-Y}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}+2\right)d_3 \\
 & + \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon^2}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}f_0 + \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}k^2}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}f_2 + \sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-3B}f_3 = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{2}{3} \left[\frac{(B-Y)k^2}{k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2} + 2k^2 + 6B - 3(2\epsilon^2 + Y + 2) \right] c_1 - \frac{4}{3} i \sqrt{2k\sqrt{Y-B}} c_2 \\
& + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-2k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6)}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} c_3 + \frac{2k\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} d_1 \\
& + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}(-k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6)\epsilon}{3(-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2)} d_2 + \frac{2}{3} k \left(\frac{Y-B}{-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2} - 4 \right) \epsilon d_3 \\
& + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon^2}{-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6} f_0 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}[2k^2 - 3(\epsilon^2 + 2)]}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} f_2 + \frac{4}{3} i \sqrt{2k\sqrt{Y-3B}} f_3 = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{2}{3} \epsilon \left(\frac{B-Y}{-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2} + 4 \right) k c_1 + \frac{4}{3} i \sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon c_2 + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k}{-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6} c_3 \\
& + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-3k^2 + 2\epsilon^2 + 6)}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} d_1 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}(3k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 6)k}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} d_2 \\
& + \frac{2}{3} \left[6k^2 - 2\epsilon^2 + 7B - 4Y + \frac{(k^2 - 2)(B-Y)}{-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2} - 6 \right] d_3 \\
& + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-3k^2 + 2\epsilon^2 + 6)}{3(-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2)} f_0 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon k^2}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} f_2 - \frac{4}{3} i \sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-3B}\epsilon f_3 = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y} c_2 + \frac{4}{3} i k \sqrt{3B+Y} c_3 + \frac{4}{3} i \sqrt{3B+Y} \epsilon d_1 + \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{2}(-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 3B + Y + 3) f_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{4}{3} i k \sqrt{Y-3B} c_1 - \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B} c_2 + \frac{4}{3} i \sqrt{Y-3B} \epsilon d_3 + \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{2}(3k^2 - 3\epsilon^2 + 3B - Y - 3) f_3 = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

The rank of the matrix referring to this system equals 10. After removing the rows 5 and 8, the rank of the matrix remains the same. Therefore, we have the equivalent system of only 10 equations

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}(2k^2 - 4\epsilon^2 - 7)}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} c_1 + \left(4k^2 - \frac{4}{3}(3\epsilon^2 + Y) \right) c_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}(2k^2 - 4\epsilon^2 - 7)}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} c_3 \\
& + \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-4k^2 + 2\epsilon^2 + 5)}{3(-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2)} d_1 + \frac{16k\epsilon(2\epsilon^2 + 3)}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} d_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-4k^2 + 2\epsilon^2 + 5)}{3(-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2)} d_3 \\
& + \frac{[-2\epsilon^4 + 6(2k^2 + Y - 2)\epsilon^2 + 6(k^2 - 2)(k^2 - Y)]}{3(k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2)} f_0 - \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y} f_1 \\
& + \frac{2}{3} \left(-11k^2 - 9\epsilon^2 - 9Y + \frac{4k^2 - 8k^4}{-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2} - 12 \right) f_2 - \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B} f_3 = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}}{-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6} c_1 + \left[4k^2 - \frac{4}{3}(3\epsilon^2 + Y + 6) \right] c_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}}{-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6} c_3 \\
& - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6} d_1 + \frac{16}{3} k \epsilon \left(\frac{1}{k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2} - 1 \right) d_2 + \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon}{-3k^2 + 3\epsilon^2 + 6} d_3 \\
& + \frac{2}{3} \left(-3k^2 - \epsilon^2 + 3Y + \frac{8 - 4k^2}{-k^2 + \epsilon^2 + 2} - 4 \right) f_0 - \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y} f_1 \\
& + \left[\frac{2}{3} k^2 \left(\frac{4}{k^2 - \epsilon^2 - 2} - 1 \right) - 2(\epsilon^2 + Y) \right] f_2 - \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B} f_3 = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}c_1 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}c_3 \\
 & -\frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_1 - \frac{4[k^2(4\epsilon^2+3Y+3)-3(Y+1)(\epsilon^2+2)]}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 \\
 & +\frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_3 + \frac{4k\epsilon(-3k^2+\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_0 + \left(\frac{8\epsilon k^3}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6} + 4\epsilon k\right)f_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}(2k^2-4\epsilon^2-5)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_1 + \left(-4k^2+4\epsilon^2+\frac{4Y}{3}\right)c_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}(2k^2-4\epsilon^2-5)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_3 \\
 & +\frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-4k^2+2\epsilon^2+7)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_1 + \frac{16k(2k^2-3)\epsilon}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 - \frac{4i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-4k^2+2\epsilon^2+7)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_3 \\
 & +\frac{2}{3}\left[k^2+3\epsilon^2-9Y+\frac{4(2k^4-7k^2+6)}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}\right]f_0 + \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 \\
 & +\left[-\frac{2(k^2-9\epsilon^2-6)k^2}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}-2(\epsilon^2+Y)\right]f_2 + \frac{4}{3}\sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B}f_3 = 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +\frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-2k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_1 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}c_2 \\
 & +\frac{2}{3}\left[\frac{(B+Y)k^2}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}+2k^2-6B-3(2\epsilon^2+Y+2)\right]c_3 + \frac{2}{3}k\left(\frac{B+Y}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}-4\right)\epsilon d_1 \\
 & -\frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)\epsilon}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_2 + \frac{2k\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_3 \\
 & +\frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon^2}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_0 - \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{3B+Y}f_1 - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{B+Y}[2k^2-3(\epsilon^2+2)]}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_2 = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}c_1 - \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon c_2 + \frac{2}{3}\epsilon\left(\frac{B+Y}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2}+4\right)kc_3 \\
& + \frac{2}{3}\left[6k^2-2\epsilon^2-7B-4Y + \frac{(k^2-2)(B+Y)}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2} - 6\right]d_1 \\
& - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)k}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-3k^2+2\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_3 \\
& - \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon(-3k^2+2\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}f_0 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{3B+Y}\epsilon f_1 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k^2}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}f_2 = 0, \\
& + \frac{2}{3}\left[\frac{(B-Y)k^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2-2} + 2k^2 + 6B - 3(2\epsilon^2 + Y + 2)\right]c_1 - \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}c_2 \\
& + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-2k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}c_3 + \frac{2k\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_1 \\
& + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}(-k^2+3\epsilon^2+6)\epsilon}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}d_2 + \frac{2}{3}k\left(\frac{Y-B}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}-4\right)\epsilon d_3 \\
& + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon^2}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}f_0 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-B}[2k^2-3(\epsilon^2+2)]}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_2 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}k\sqrt{Y-3B}f_3 = 0, \\
& \frac{2}{3}\epsilon\left(\frac{B-Y}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2}+4\right)kc_1 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon c_2 + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}\epsilon k}{-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+6}c_3 \\
& + \frac{2\sqrt{Y-B}\sqrt{B+Y}(-3k^2+2\epsilon^2+6)}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_1 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}(3k^2-\epsilon^2-6)k}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}d_2 \\
& + \frac{2}{3}\left[6k^2-2\epsilon^2+7B-4Y + \frac{(k^2-2)(B-Y)}{-k^2+\epsilon^2+2} - 6\right]d_3 \\
& + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon(-3k^2+2\epsilon^2+6)}{3(-k^2+\epsilon^2+2)}f_0 + \frac{2i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-B}\epsilon k^2}{3(k^2-\epsilon^2-2)}f_2 - \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-3B}\epsilon f_3 = 0, \\
& \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}\sqrt{B+Y}\sqrt{3B+Y}c_2 + \frac{4}{3}ik\sqrt{3B+Y}c_3 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{3B+Y}\epsilon d_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}(-3k^2+3\epsilon^2+3B+Y+3)f_1 = 0, \\
& \frac{4}{3}ik\sqrt{Y-3B}c_1 - \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}\sqrt{Y-3B}\sqrt{Y-B}c_2 + \frac{4}{3}i\sqrt{Y-3B}\epsilon d_3 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}(3k^2-3\epsilon^2+3B-Y-3)f_3 = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

In accordance with the identity (27), we may eliminate the variable f_0 . In this way, we obtain the homogeneous system of 9 equations for 9 variables. From vanishing its determinant we derive a 7-th order equation with respect to the variable $Z = \epsilon^2$:

$$\begin{aligned}
& -16(B^2+1)Z^7 - 8[3B^4 + (-14k^2 + 10Y + 27)B^2 - 14k^2 + 12Y + 22]Z^6 \\
& + 4\{3(12k^2 - 5Y - 18)B^4 - [84k^4 - 12(10Y + 27)k^2 + Y(40Y + 209) + 296]B^2 \\
& - 4[21k^4 - 6(6Y + 11)k^2 + Y(15Y + 58) + 49]\}Z^5 \\
& + 2\{9B^6 - 3[60k^4 - 10(5Y + 18)k^2 + 6Y^2 + 50Y + 121]B^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +2 [140k^6 - 30(10Y + 27)k^4 + 5(Y(40Y + 209) + 296)k^2 - 2(4Y(Y(5Y + 37) + 109) + 395)] B^2 \\
 & \quad + 40(k^2 - Y - 1) [7k^4 - (11Y + 26)k^2 + Y(4Y + 21) + 23] Z^4 \\
 & + \{-9 [8k^2 + 5(Y - 3)] B^6 + 3 [160k^6 - 40(5Y + 18)k^4 + 8(6Y^2 + 50Y + 121)k^2 + Y(4Y(Y + 3) - 93) \\
 & \quad - 257] B^4 - 8 [70k^8 - 20(10Y + 27)k^6 + 5(Y(40Y + 209) + 296)k^4 \\
 & \quad - 4[4Y(Y(5Y + 37) + 109) + 395]k^2 + (Y + 1)[Y(Y(10Y + 77) + 334) + 480]] B^2 \\
 & \quad - 80(-k^2 + Y + 1)^2 [7k^4 - 10(Y + 3)k^2 + Y(3Y + 22) + 31] Z^3 \\
 & \quad + \{9 [12k^4 + 15(Y - 3)k^2 + 2((Y - 17)Y + 12)] B^6 \\
 & \quad - 3 [120k^8 - 40(5Y + 18)k^6 + 12(6Y^2 + 50Y + 121)k^4 \\
 & \quad + 3[Y(4Y(Y + 3) - 93) - 257]k^2 - (Y + 1)[Y(4Y(Y + 8) + 79) + 249]] B^4 \\
 & \quad + 8(k^2 - Y - 1) [42k^8 - 3(36Y + 121)k^6 + (92Y^2 + 574Y + 1117)k^4 \\
 & \quad - (Y(28Y^2 + 222Y + 925) + 1253)k^2 + (Y + 1)(Y(Y(2Y + 9) + 77) + 187)] B^2 \\
 & \quad + 16(k^2 - Y - 1)^3 [21k^4 - 3(9Y + 34)k^2 + Y(6Y + 67) + 121] Z^2 \\
 & \quad + \{-9 [8k^6 + 15(Y - 3)k^4 + 4((Y - 17)Y + 12)k^2 - 2(Y + 1)(7Y - 23)] B^6 \\
 & + 3 [48k^{10} - 20(5Y + 18)k^8 + 8(6Y^2 + 50Y + 121)k^6 + 3(Y(4Y(Y + 3) - 93) - 257)k^4 \\
 & \quad - 2(Y + 1)(Y(4Y(Y + 8) + 79) + 249)k^2 - (Y + 1)^2(Y(4Y + 39) - 181)] B^4 \\
 & \quad - 4(-k^2 + Y + 1)^2 [28k^8 - 4(16Y + 67)k^6 + (Y(44Y + 325) + 916)k^4 \\
 & \quad - 2(Y(Y(4Y + 25) + 203) + 530)k^2 - (Y + 1)(7Y(Y + 7) + 156)] B^2 \\
 & \quad - 16(-k^2 + Y + 1)^4 (7k^4 - 2(4Y + 19)k^2 + Y(Y + 22) + 51) Z \\
 & \quad + 9B^6(2k^2 + Y + 1) [(k^2 - 4)^2 + 2(k^2 - 7)Y] k^2 + 15(Y + 1) \\
 & - 3B^4(k^2 - Y - 1) [8k^{10} - 4(3Y + 16)k^8 + 2(12Y + 89)k^6 + (Y(4Y(Y + 9) + 109) - 79) k^4 \\
 & \quad + 2(Y + 1) ((2Y + 15) - 164) k^2 - 3(Y + 1)^2(3Y + 49)] \\
 & \quad + 4B^2(k^2 - Y - 1)^3 [4k^8 - 2(4Y + 21)k^6 + (Y(4Y + 35) + 158)k^4 \\
 & + (Y(7Y - 5) - 186)k^2 - 6(Y + 1)(3Y + 19)] + 16(k^2 - 3)(k^2 - Y - 3)(k^2 - Y - 1)^5 = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account the equality $Y = -2BN - B$, we can calculate the roots $Z =$

ϵ^2 . Depending on the values of dimensionless amplitude of the magnetic field B and the quantum number k, N , we get both physically interpretable energy real levels and a number of complex levels, the last are not physically interpretable, and relate to the so called anomalous solutions. Below, only one example is given (there the symbol “.” corresponds to complex or imaginary energies).

6. Conclusion

In the present paper we have studied the theory of the massive spin 2 particle in the presence of an external uniform magnetic field. For the energy values we derive a 7-th order algebraic equation, there arise physically interpretable energy values and complex ones, the last relate to anomalous solutions.

Example.

$$B = 30, k = 5, N = 1, \dots, 15$$

-1085.79	-36.214	24	25.919	. .	172.95
-893.301	-108.70	23.877	26.878	. .	242.658
-621.	-261.	23.822	27.223	. .	310.167
.	.	23.780	27.419	. .	376.419
.	.	23.745	27.564	. .	441.841
.	.	23.713	27.686	. .	506.664
.	.	23.683	27.796	. .	571.032
.	.	23.655	27.899	. .	635.038
.	.	23.629	27.997	.	698.751
.	.	23.604	28.093	. .	762.218
23.580	28.186	.	.	. .	825.477
23.557	28.277	.	.	. .	888.557
23.535	28.367	.	.	. .	951.48
23.514	28.456	.	.	. .	1014.27
23.493	28.543	.	.	. .	1076.93

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